

“Synthesis of Floral Mediated Nanoparticles from Mimosa pudica and its Antibacterial activity against Clinical Pathogens”

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ABSTRACT

Mimosa pudica flower is creeping annual or perennial herb it has been identify as “Laajalu” in Ayurveda and has been found to have antiasthematic, aphorodisiac, analgesic and antidepressant. In the present study floral mediated nanoparticles of Mimosa pudica were revealed using antibacterial activity analysis. For Synthesis of floral mediated nanoparticles M.pudica flowers were shed-dried and flower extract were prepared. Synthesized nanoparticles of flower extract were kept for dark incubation and colour was changed indicating positive result .The antibacterial activity of synthesized nanoparticles were tested against clinical pathogen E.coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa and S. aureus at different molar concentration of synthesized nanoparticles ranging from 6M, 8M, 10M and absolute. The maximum zones of inhibition were 1.5mm, 2mm, and 1.4mm respectively.

Keywords: Mimosa pudica, Clinical pathogens, floral nanoparticles, antibacterial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Plants and plant product is the natural hub for traditional medicines from thousands and thousands of year throughout the world. As per WHOM definition traditional medicines are the derivative of plant products and have been used for cure illness with or without minimal processing. These plants derived compound formed as a standalone platform for the development of modern medicines. About 77%-80% of global population uses these herbal medicines in primary health care since plant based product are considered as safe without any side effects and cost effective. (Martins, E.2014).

Herbal medicine involves the use of plants for medicinal purposes. The term “herb” includes leaves, stems, flowers, fruits, seeds, roots, rhizomes and bark. There can be little doubt that the use of plants for healing purposes is the most ancient form of medicine known. The quest for plants with medicinal properties continues to receive attention as scientists are in need of plants, particularly of ethno botanical significance for a complete range of biological activities, which ranges from antibiotic to anticancer. Several plants and herb species used traditionally have potential antimicrobial and antiviral properties and this has raised the optimism of scientists about the future of phytoantimicrobial agents (Palwinder et al., 2011).

The theoretical concept of nanotechnology was first described in 1989 by the physicist, Richant Feynman. Metal nanoparticles (NPs) with distinct physicochemical properties have gained considerable attention in the last few decades. Due to their ultra-small size and large surface area to volume ratio, a great interest.As a result of their unique optoelectronic and physicochemical properties, NP’s have number of applications(Kumar et al.,2020).

Nanoparticles such as metals, metal oxides and semiconductor materials (quantum dots) are one of nanomaterials that have attracted the attention of researchers because of their unique properties. Nanoparticles and nanomaterials represent an emerging technology that has the potential to have an impact on an incredibly wide number of industries including medical and pharmaceutical industries, but there needs to develop clean, non-toxic and environmental friendly methods for the synthesis and assembly of nanoparticles. The use of biological system in this area is rapidly gaining importance due to its growing success (Ganesh et al., 2009).

The nanoparticles are of different shape, size and structure and differ from 1 am to 100 nm in size. Some nanoparticles are crystalline or amorphous with single or multi crystal solids either loose or agglomerated numerous synthesis methods are either being developed or improved to enhance the properties and reduce the production costs. Some methods are modified to achieve process specific nanoparticles to increase their optical, mechanical, physical and

chemical properties. A vast development in the instrumentation has led to an improved nanoparticle characterisation and subsequent application.

Nanobiotechnology is a promising interdisciplinary field with interesting application in different scientific fields such as medicine, biotechnology, chemistry, physics, and material science. Metallic nanoparticles are attractive due to their potential and application in novel technologies. Among the metallic nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have attracted the attention of researcher in the field of science and technology due to their vast biological application. (Arvindnathan et al., 2015)

Mimosa pudica is the herb first formally described by the Carl Linnaeus in 1753 which a creeping annual or perennial herb of the pea family fabaceae gives alkaloids, steriodals, sapgenins, falvonoids, tannins, unsaturated sterols and essential oil .Mimosa pudica is derived from the word “mimic” means to allude, to sensitivity of leaves and “pudica” means hashful, retiring or shrinking because of its curious nature and easy procreation.

In Western medicine, Mimosa root is used for treating insomnia, irritability, premenstrual syndrome (PMS). Menorrhagia, hemorrhoids, skin wounds, and diarrhea. It is also used to treat whooping cough and fevers in children, and there is some evidence to suggest that Mimosa is effective in relieving the symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis. All parts of the Mimosa plant are reportedly toxic if taken directly.

Its consumption is not recommended to pregnant or nursing ladies. Due to these reports, it seems to be best to consult a physician before using Mimosa internally. Researches regarding safety in young children or those with severe liver or kidney disease have not been found (Joseph et al., 2013)

Mimosa Pudica has major pharmacological activities such as wound healing activity, antidepressant action, hyperglycemic effect, diuretic effect, antifertility activity, anti-hepatotoxic and antioxidant potential, antimicrobial properties, antifungal activity, antiviral properties. These herbs play beneficial role in haemorrhagic disease and gynaecological disorders. Mimosa pudica is a plant used by the local people to treat snakebite patients, is effective to neutralize the lithelity and toxic enzyme of venom (Marimuthuet al., 2011) M.Pudica is rich in phytochemical such as tannins, terpenoids, flavonoids, sterols, glycosides, alkaloids, and mimosine. (Kshemaet al., 2014)

Biomimetric synthesis emerged as the most promising method for the synthesis of AgNPs. Several biotic components like plant extracts, fungi, bacteria, yeast, milk, and oilcakes have been reported for synthesis of AgNPs. Among the biological components, the use of plant extract for the production of AgNPs is potentially advantageous for the production of AgNPs is potentially advantageous and due to their low cost, viability, and scale up. (Salvin et al., 2017).

In this study, we had utilize medicinally important flowers of M. Pudica as a green source, to synthesize green nanoparticles and antimicrobial activity of floral mediated nanoparticles of Mimosa pudica was tested against various clinical pathogenic bacteria such as Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, and Staphylococcus aureus at different concentrations of nanoparticles.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Collection and extraction of flower extract

Mimosa pudica flowers have been collected from local area of Chh. Sambhaji Nagar during July 2023 for research study. Then flowers have been shade-dried thoroughly and weight upto 5 gm and were grounded in motor and pestle. The well smashed paste of M. pudica flowers were mixed with 50 ml of distilled water and then the mixture was boiled at 60°C for 5-10 minutes. It was kept aside for cool down. The mixtures have been filtered through whatsmann filter paper No.1. The filter crude flower extract was used for further purpose.

Synthesis of M. pudica floral-mediated nanoparticles

For 10 ml of crude floral extract, 90 ml of 1Mm silver nitrate solution have been added to that conical flask having proportion with 1:10 ratio and keep for dark incubation. After the colour change, the nanoparticles solutions have been subjected to multiple centrifugation. Then nanoparticles were dissolved in 30% of dimethyl sulfoxide.

Antibacterial activity of floral nanoparticles against clinical pathogens

The clinical pathogens were streak on nutrient agar plates. Using different molar concentration (6M, 8M, 10M and absolute) of synthesized nanoparticles antibacterial activity was performed against clinical pathogen (E. coli, Pseudomonads aeruginosa and S. aureus) by Agar well Diffusion Method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Collection and extraction of flower extract

In this study, the conventional method of developing nanoparticles are costly and produce very toxic products, so the need of hours to reduce the risk of toxicity in the environment from different chemicals used in the physical and chemical methods. The alternative approach found develops floral mediated nanoparticles.

Mimosa Pudica flowers was collected from the local area of Chh. Sambhajinagar and use for further study. For preparation of flower extract around 5gm Shaded dried flowers was boiled in the 300ml of distilled water on boiling water bath and then filtered through whatsmann filter paper.

Fig 1: Mimosa pudica Flowers

Fig 2: Shaded dried flowers

Fig 3: Flower extract

Synthesis of Nanoparticles

For synthesis of nanoparticles 0.015g silver nitrate were added to 100 ml of flower extract in conical and kept for dark incubation, covering with aluminium foil. Flower extract colour was changed from yellow to Muddy green showing presence of Nanoparticles. The nanoparticle solution has been subjected to multiple centrifugations and pellets were collected. The green synthesized M. pudica floral mediated nanoparticles were characterized by UV Vis spectroscopy ranging from 100 nm to 900 nm. Synthesized floral mediated nanoparticles from Mimosa pudica shows peak at 320 nm.

Fig 4: After dark incubation flower extract colour change from yellow to muddy green

Fig 5: UV- Vis absorption spectrum of Mimosa pudica floral mediated nanoparticle synthesis

Antibacterial Activity against Clinical Pathogens:

In this study of Synthesis of Floral mediated from M. pudicawe have focused on the antibacterial activity of synthesis floral mediated nanoparticles against various clinical pathogens like E.coli, Pseudomonads aeroginasa and S. aureus. Thus the MpFNp could be the potent alternative to kill antibiotic resistance. The clinical pathogens E.coli

(ATCC25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC27853), *Staphylococcus Aureus* (ATCC25923) were streak on nutrient agar slant for further study. Different molar concentration of synthesized nanoparticles sample was prepared from 6M to 10M and their antibacterial activity was checked by agar well diffusion method. The presence of clear zone around the MpFNp well suggesting that the MpFNp possessed antibacterial activity which is able to inhibit the growth of clinical pathogens.

The antibacterial activity of synthesized nanoparticles were tested against clinical pathogen *E.coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* at different molar concentration of synthesized nanoparticles ranging from 6M, 8M, 10M and absolute. The maximum zone of inhibition was 1.5mm, 2mm, and 1.4mm respectively. The exact mechanism of antibacterial effect of AgNPs against various bacteria is not understood. This might be due to the electrostatic attraction between the positively charged nanoparticles and the negatively charged cell membrane of micro-organism. Due to the electro-static attraction, metallic AgNPs attach to the surface of the cell membrane, thereby affecting its permeability and damaging cell respiration behavior.

Fig 6: Agar well diffusion for antibacterial activity against clinical pathogen

SUMMARY CONCLUSION

The proposed method is simple and green approach to synthesize silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using the aqueous *Mimosa pudica* root extract. The characterization with UV-Vis spectrophotometer is the preliminary evidence for the formation of silver nanoparticles which shows peak at 320nm.

Floral mediated nanoparticles synthesis from *Mimosa pudica* floral extract exhibit potent antibacterial and antibiofilm activity against clinical pathogens *E.coli* (ATCC25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC27853) and *S. aureus* (ATCC29923). From the result of this study, it can be concluded that *Mimosa pudica* contain bioactive compound and found to have strong antibacterial activity which can be alternative method for antibiotic resistant

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